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Modeling Pre-Anthropogenic Topography: A Reconstruction in the Perugia Center Using Subsoil Data

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Abstract— This study aimed at developing a digital elevation model of the city center of Perugia, the capital city of Umbria region (Central Italy), to approximate the terrain as it existed prior to human settlement, and study the anthropogenic deposits identified in different locations of the study area. In fact, the foundation of the city dates back 3000 years, and human modifications played a key role in shaping the area. Main modifications exist in the city center area, located on a series of hilltops. Data about the thickness of anthropogenic deposits, from approximately 200 boreholes, allowed us to reconstruct the pre-settlement topography. Numerical interpolation of data about thickness of deposits revealed key areas with significant modifications, mostly located close the watersheds' drainage divide, where the fluvial and gravitational erosional processes acted in the past. In contrast, other areas close to the top of the hill displayed evidence of artificial leveling. This research enhances the geomorphological mapping of Perugia by precisely delineating the extent and thickness of anthropogenic deposits and allows to recognize and perimeter inactive landforms, currently invisible on the topographic surface. Knowledge of the pre-settlement topography provides critical insights into the historical evolution of the landscape and offers valuable support for urban planning and stability assessments. The methodology holds promise for application in similar urban contexts across Umbria and beyond.

I. INTRODUCTION

The understanding of geological elements, such as the type and distribution of rocks, along with the past and present geomorphological evolution, is essential for understanding the

development of cities. In this context, urban geology plays a key role in identifying natural hazards and preserving geological heritage, especially in cities with high cultural value, whose historic centers experienced significant transformations of the original morphology over time. This makes the application of urban geology in the assessment of risks and available resources even more relevant, thus contributing to more sustainable and resilient territorial planning [1].

Over the centuries, urban settlements have been transforming the original topography, particularly in areas with hilly or irregular morphology. In Perugia, Central Italy, such transformations were necessary to prevent landslides and enable urban development. In this work, we developed a digital elevation model (DEM), with anthropogenic deposits removed, providing an approximation of the pre-settlement topography [2].

This analysis allows determining the thickness of anthropogenic deposits in the area, and studying the modifications introduced over time. The results support the geomorphological assessment in urban areas where the anthropogenic process modify, even drastically, the original topographic settlement [3]. Identifying the filling and leveling areas supports the creation of a geomorphological map, allowing identifying and delineating anthropic landforms and natural features modified by human activities [4].

Accurate knowledge of human modifications may help in planning sustainable cities, where the geological and

geomorphological arrangement are the first step for the assessment of natural hazards, conservation of the value of geodiversity, and study the link with the biosphere [5-7].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

For the creation of a pre-settlement DEM, we used data on the thickness of anthropogenic fill, obtained through boreholes drilled in the urban area of Perugia, specifically within the historic center, including areas both inside and near the boundaries of the Etruscan and Medieval walls. This information was sourced from the 'Geognostic and Geophysical Investigations Database' provided open access by Open Data Umbria (accessible at <https://dati.regione.umbria.it/dataset/banca-dati-indagini-geognostiche-geofisiche>). The data, available in KMZ format for visualization in Google Earth, includes reports on 265 areas corresponding to regional technical maps. Reviewing the Google Earth reports of individual investigations in their original PDF format, we focused on boreholes or surveys containing stratigraphic information, both in the presence and in absence of anthropogenic deposits.

B. Method

We used a database to store information about the wells, each assigned a unique ID along with thickness of the anthropogenic deposit, data acquisition year, location details, borehole identifier, responsible company, and X-Y coordinates. Projecting the database onto the map ensured consistency between the recorded locations and their descriptions, making it easier to identify and remove duplicates. Only 5% of the 300 entries were duplicate, leaving 285 different boreholes for the study. These boreholes correspond to drilling conducted between 1969 and 2024.

The borehole database was imported into ArcGIS Pro software for the interpolation process, using the LiDAR DEM as the current terrain baseline. In ArcGIS Pro, the "Extract Values to Points" tool helped associating each well's location with the corresponding pixel in the LiDAR DEM, generating a new shapefile. This shapefile contains both the anthropogenic deposit thickness and a data column with the current surface elevation at each well location. Using these two datasets and the "Field Calculator" tool, a new column was created to represent the original terrain elevation by subtracting the deposit thickness.

The 285 well points were distributed across the historic center of Perugia. Considering the city's morphology, characterized by hills and valleys, the points were grouped into clusters based on proximity. This approach enabled the independent analysis of each area and allowed for a more refined selection of wells by excluding clusters that extended beyond the study area or points that did not associate with any cluster. Using these clusters and local knowledge, nine regions were defined for interpolating the

morphology of the anthropogenic deposits, ultimately utilizing data from 221 wells (Table 1).

The terrain elevation data, obtained by subtracting the deposit thickness, was interpolated using a simplified approach based on deterministic 'Topo to Raster' tool in ArcGIS Pro, also known as ANUDEM [8-9]. This method was chosen because it was specifically developed to produce hydrologically correct digital elevation models (DEMs) capable of capturing abrupt variations and providing accurate representations of ridges and streams [8-10]. Such capabilities align with our objective of identifying possible paleo-channels that may have been overlain by anthropogenic deposits.

The use of kriging was considered less appropriate in this context, as the low density of data points within each cluster did not support the construction of a reliable variogram model. Furthermore, the data do not represent a natural, undisturbed phenomenon, but rather terrain altered by human activity, which reduces the applicability of standard geostatistical assumptions [11].

To refine the model, random points were extracted from the LiDAR-derived DEM. A buffer zone was applied around each borehole to ensure that random points were not placed too close to, or directly on, these measured locations. The random LiDAR points were then combined with the borehole data for interpolation. The resulting terrain model—representing the pre-settlement surface—was compared to the current LiDAR topography using the *Raster Calculator*. Areas where current elevation exceeds pre-settlement elevation were identified as anthropogenic deposits and highlighted as polygonal features.

Table I. Number of wells for each interpolation area in Figure 1.

Area ID	Name	No. wells
A	Elce	4
B	Cupa & San Francesco	103
C	Bulagaio	14
D	Arconi	34
E	Santa Margherita 1	5
F	Santa Margherita 2	10
G	Sant'Anna	31
H	Rocca Paolina	13
I	Bucaccio	7
-	Non included	64
Total		285

Figure 1. (I) Current digital elevation of Perugia based on LiDAR-derived DEM. (II) Interpolated pre-anthropogenic digital elevation of Perugia. Interpolated areas: **A.** Elce, **B.** Cupa and San Francesco, **C.** Bulagaio, **D.** Arconi, **E.** Santa Margherita 2, **F.** Santa Margherita 1, **G.** Sant'Anna, **H.** Rocca Paolina, **I.** Buccaccio.

Deposits thinner than one meter were excluded from analysis, as such minor changes are commonly found in urban environments due to structural modifications and do not necessarily indicate significant anthropogenic fill. Figure 1 shows the DEM generated through interpolation and compares it with the current topography, highlighting with polygons the areas of anthropogenic deposits.

To evaluate the interpolation robustness, five repetitions were performed using different sets of random points. The variability among these five interpolated models was assessed by calculating the standard deviation at each pixel. To determine the model with the lowest relative variability, the coefficient of variation (CV)—defined as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean elevation—was computed for each pixel across models.

III. RESULTS

The interpolated areas, derived from borehole data, were primarily located in the headwater streams, including zones denoted in Figure 1 and Table I as Elce (A), Cupa (B), Bulagaio (C), Arconi (D), Santa Margherita 1 and 2 (E, F), and Sant'Anna (G). Notably, the last three belong to the same hydrographic basin of Santa Margherita. Conversely, areas like San Francesco (B), Buccaccio (I), and Rocca Paolina (H) revealed fills in summit zones, suggesting processes of terrain leveling.

The interpolation performed using the *Topo to Raster* tool produced a topographic surface consistent with the area's natural relief. Among the five evaluated models, the maximum standard deviation was 8.18 meters, indicating a relatively stable interpolation. The resulting DEM clearly reflects the topographic pattern of Perugia, where the city center is situated at a higher elevation that gradually decreases toward the surrounding valleys (Figure 1). This elevation gradient is especially evident in areas such as Cupa (B), Bulagaio (C), Arconi (D), Santa Margherita (E, F), and Sant'Anna (G).

A comparison between the most recent LiDAR-based and the interpolated (representing topography without anthropogenic deposits) DEMs allowed identifying deposit depths, based on point data. Thickness ranged from 2 to 20 m, with the largest values concentrated in areas like Cupa-San Francesco, Arconi, Sant'Anna, and Santa Margherita, corresponding to the headwaters of watercourses.

Areas with fewer than 10 boreholes for interpolation, such as Santa Margherita 1 and 2, Buccaccio, and Elce, had limited coverage. On the other hand, zones like Rocca Paolina, Bulagaio, Sant'Anna, and Arconi contained an intermediate number of data points, ranging from 13 to 34. This facilitated broader coverage in some cases, such as in Sant'Anna, or the confirmation of highly excavated zones like Arconi, thanks to the availability of nearby

points. Cupa and San Francesco emerged as the areas with the highest borehole density, with 103 points.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In an ideal spatial interpolation procedure, a large and evenly distributed set of borehole data would be preferable. However, in Perugia, most boreholes were drilled in specific areas for infrastructural purposes, resulting in a high data density in limited zones, such as near the churches of San Filippo Neri and San Francesco al Prato. Conversely, there are examples of isolated boreholes with significant fill information, complicating the understanding of surrounding morphology due to the lack of additional control points. For instance, one borehole in Santa Margherita recorded a thickness of 25.8 meters, and one borehole in Cupa recorded 20 meters. To ensure analytical reliability, the study included only areas with thicknesses equal to or greater than 2 meters of anthropogenic fill.

The spatial interpolation of measured deposit thickness proven very useful. In fact, although information on anthropogenic fills was available, their spatial distribution in the terrain was not well understood. Additionally, the results shed light on morphological changes in the headwater streams, such as Santa Margherita, Sant'Anna, and Cupa, highlighting how these areas were modified by human settlements and by natural erosion. Furthermore, the interpolation allowed for the identification of artificially leveled zones, such as Rocca Paolina and San Francesco al Prato.

Although it was not a statistical interpolation but a deterministic one using the ANUDEM method, the results could be evaluated by calculating the standard deviation among them, reaching a maximum difference of 8 meters between the interpolations.

This research contributes significantly to the ongoing geomorphological cartography project in central Perugia. The data enable the accurate identification of anthropogenic fill areas and provide detailed information on the thickness and depth of these deposits.

A few key areas, including via Pascoli and Corso Vannucci (not shown in the figure), contained a limited number of boreholes (fewer than two), preventing a meaningful interpolation.

It was also essential to include boreholes with null fill values or with thickness less than 2 meters, in the interpolation process, as this ensured a proper delineation of areas with deposits and enhanced confidence in identifying zones likely unaffected by anthropogenic fills.

Finally, this methodology is recommended for similar urban areas, both in Umbria and in other Italian regions with available fill data. It offers valuable insights into the evolution of relief in these zones and supports assessments of urban stability.

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